

Hysterectomy – Which Approach?

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Abstract:

Hysterectomy operation is frequently performed on women. In the era of minimal invasive surgery, the route of hysterectomy depends upon numerous clinical variables. The aim of this study was to evaluate & suggest the appropriate approach for hysterectomy.

A total of 250 patients were included in the presents study; they were divided, into three categories: Category I included 50 patients of Pelvic Organ Prolapse (POP) for Vaginal Hysterectomy (VH), Category II included 40 patients who underwent Non Descent Vaginal Hysterectomy (NDVH), Category III included 160 patients who had Total Abdominal Hysterectomy (TAH). Operative time, hemorrhage, wound infection, post- operative analgesia, febrile morbidity, hospital stay and recovery were recorded for each patient.

Indications for hysterectomy were POP, abnormal uterine bleeding (AUB) and fibroid uterus. The study period showed a gradual increase in number of NDVH. Perioperative blood loss, post operative pain score, hospital stay; cost was less in patients with VH/NDVH. Uncomplicated, fast and cost effective technique for removal of uterus remains VH & NDVH.

Non Descent Vaginal Hysterectomy is gaining increased acceptability among patients being minimally invasive with no visible scar.

Key Words: NDVH, TAH, Vaginal Hystrectomy, Microalbuminuria.

Introduction:

Hysterectomy is the commonest major gynaecological surgery performed in women. The first successful Total Abdominal Hysterectomy (TAH) was performed by Charles Clay at Manchester (1843A.D.). Hippocrate (Fifth century B.C.) was the first to refer about Vaginal Hysterectomy (VH) for prolapse and inversion of uterus. Vaginal Hysterectomy was documented by Soreanus of Ephesus (120 A.D.) but Conrad Langenbeck is credited with the first successful V H (1813 A.D.).

Traditionally, the uterus has been removed by abdominal route that gives the opportunity to inspect the ovaries, a major advantage. The vaginal route is being reserved for Pelvic Organ Prolapse (POP). In the 1990's, Laproscopic Assisted Vaginal Hysterectomy (LAVH)¹ developed and gained acceptance. Many Gynecologists opt to develop their skills for the more sophisticated technique of Total Laproscopic Hysterectomy (TLH). Today radical hysterectomy & bilateral pelvic lymphadenectomy is being performed laproscopically² and robotic assistance³ is being used. Single incision TLH, single port of entry i.e. embryonic

Natural Orifice Transumbilical Endoscopic Surgery (NOTES)⁴ has evolved further. The emphasis on minimally invasive surgery has lead to a resurgence of interest and importance of VH for non-prolapse indications i.e. Non-descent Vaginal Hysterectomy (NDVH) as the scarless hysterectomy.

Ovaries and other abdominal organs may be appraised by non-invasive means such as ultrasonography, computerised tomography, magnetic resonance imaging, positron emission tomography and tumour markers or diagnostic laproscopy. The aim of this study was to evaluate & suggest the appropriate approach for hysterectomy.

Material & Methods:

This study, a retrospective analysis was undertaken in the Department of Obstetrics & Gynecology, NIMS Medical College, Jaipur from January 2009 - July 2011. Patients undergoing emergency or radical hysterectomy were excluded from the study. A total of 250 patients were divided into three categories: Category I (n=50) Patients of Pelvic Organ Prolapse (POP) for Vaginal Hysterectomy (VH), Category II (n =40) Patients who underwent Non Descent Vaginal Hysterectomy (NDVH) and Category III (n =160) Patients who had Total Abdominal Hysterectomy (TAH).

All hysterectomies were done under spinal

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anaesthesia. All abdominal hysterectomies were performed by Richardson’s technique⁵. Oophorectomy was done based on age and disease as per patient’s informed consent. Non Descent Vaginal Hysterectomy was done by the Ten Step technique⁶, two cases where the uterine size was larger than 14 weeks, required morcellation technique to reduce uterine size to facilitate delivery of the uterus. Vaginal Hysterectomy for POP was done by Mayo Ward technique with pelvic floor repair as per associated defects.

All patients received antibiotic prophylaxis: either Ampicillin-Cloxacillin / Ceftriaxone plus Gentamicin or Amikacin plus Metronidazole. The time for surgery was noted from incision to completion. Blood loss was calculated by the anaesthesiologist and surgical team by totaling blood in suction bottle, soakage on mops and blood on drapes. Postoperatively, haemoglobin was estimated on day three. Patients were discharged after fourth postoperative day in the absence of pain and micturitional problems. Hospital stay was calculated from the day of surgery. Postoperative checkups were done weekly at one, two, four, six weeks after discharge. The period of convalescence was counted as number of days after discharge from hospital till full recovery.

Results:

During the study period, 250 Hysterectomies were performed; their breakup is shown in Table I. Category-I accounted for 18.33 to 20.59%; Category-II accounted for only 1.14% cases in 2009, which progressively increased to 17.65% and 35% cases in 2010 & 2011 respectively while Category-III registered a progressive fall from 78.41%, in 2009 to 61.76% to 46.67% in 2011.

Table I: Categories of Hysterectomy.

	2009 n= 88	2010 n=102	Jan - Jul 2011 n=60	Total
Category –I	18 (20.45%)	21 (20.59%)	11 (18.33%)	50
Category-II	1 (01.14%)	18 (17.65%)	21 (35.00%)	40
Category-III	69 (78.41%)	63 (61.76%)	28 (46.67%)	160
Total	88	102	60	250

Age wise distribution of the patients is shown in Table – II. The mean age of POP patients who underwent VH and repair in 2009, 2010 & 2011 were 46.4 years,

45.7 years, 47.3 years respectively. Mean ages for patients who underwent NDVH in 2009, 2010 & 2011 was 40 years, 40 years, 42.1 years respectively. Patients who had TAH in 2009, 2010 & 2011 had mean ages of 44.8 years, 45.3 years and 46.1 years.

The indications for hysterectomy for the various catorgreis is shown in Table III.

Analysis was done for measures like operative time, operative blood loss, blood transfusion, postoperative analgesia, postoperative febrile morbidity(temperature > 38°C), duration of bladder catheterization, development of urinary tract infection, postoperative wound infection and hospital stay. Other factors noted were secondary haemorrhage in the form of bleeding per vaginum, development of vault haematoma, vault granulation and non-healing ulcer over cuff, cuff cellulitis, convalescence period and recovery (Table-IV).

Discussion:

The incidence of vaginal hysterectomy (VH for POP & NDVH) was 21.59% in 2009 which rose to 38.24% and 53.33% in 2010 and 2011 respectively. In the present study VH component for POP has been 18.33% to 20.59%. In Sweden⁷ an increase in the rate of VH was recorded from about 4% in 1987 to 31% in 2003. In Finland⁸ rate of VH was reported to be 44%, Laproscopic Hysterectomy on 32% and TAH rate of 24%. A Canadian⁹ tertiary care facility reported 14% VH and 5.9% LAVH in 2001. In Nigeria¹⁰ rate for VH was 20% between 1994 to 2003. In Saudi Arabia¹¹, rate for VH was 21% between 1990 and 2002. In the present study rate of VH for POP was similar to the above studies.

Mean age of patients who underwent hysterectomy was 48.5 years in Canada⁹ and 45.7 years in Nigeria¹⁰ showing that the majority of patients undergoing hysterectomy are over 45 years of age. The NDVH group being younger due to their motivational counseling for a scar less operation, less surgical pain, early recovery & mobility.

The Canadian⁹ study revealed abnormal uterine bleeding (AUB) as the indication for hysterectomy in 37% cases. In Nigeria¹⁰ fibroid uterus was the commonest indication for hysterectomy in 62.3% cases and POP in 13.1% cases. Saudi¹¹ women underwent hysterectomy for fibroid uterus in 41.6% cases dysfunctional uterine bleeding (DUB) in 27.1%; out of those who underwent VH, 86.5% had POP. In the present study the indications for hysterectomy

Table: II Age wise distribution of the patients.

	2009	2009	2009	2010	2010	2010	2011	2011	2011
	Cat-I	Cat-II	Cat-III	Cat-I	Cat-II	Cat-III	Cat-I	Cat-II	Cat-III
>55 Yrs	4	-	11	3	-	8	2	-	6
45 – 55 Yrs	6	-	28	8	3	26	5	7	10
35 – 45 Yrs	7	1	22	9	9	20	4	9	8
< 35 Yrs	1	-	8	1	6	9	-	5	4
Totals	18	1	69	21	18	63	11	21	28

Table III: Indications for Hysterectomy

	CATEGORY- I	CATEGORY- II	CATEGORY- III
Fibroids	4#	11	37
AUB / DUB	3#	15	43
Adenomyosis	3#	9	25
Prolapse	50	-	3*
Chronic PID^	1#	2	16
Adnexal Mass / Ovarian Tumours	-	1	25
\$CIN / Cervical dysplasia	1#	2	6
Endometriosis	-	-	8
Totals	62	40	163

AUB-Abnormal uterine bleeding, DUB-Dysfunctional uterine bleeding . * patients who had large irregular fibroid uterus with anterior vaginal wall prolapse were operated abdominally and triangular piece of vagina with base superiorly was excised and walls were sutured. # 12 patients had Fibroid/AUB/DUB/Adenomyosis/CIN/PID diseases in addition to POP for whom VH with repair surgery was done. \$ CIN - Cervical Intraepithelial Neoplasia, ^ PID - Pelvic Inflammatory Disease.

Table IV: Intraoperative & Postoperative parameters

Parameters	Category-I	Category-II	Category-III
Operation time	1hr35min (1hr15min to 2hr30min)	45 min (35mins to 1hr05mins)	1hr20min (1hr05min to 2hr30min)
Intraoperative blood loss	150ml (100-400ml)	60ml (20-150ml)	250ml (80-650ml)
Blood Transfusion	2 patient	Nil	6 patient
Postoperative Analgesia	Required day-1 SOS day-2	Required day-1	Required day-1, day-2 SOS day-3
Postoperative pyrexia	2 patient	1 patient	5 patient
Bladder catheter	48-72hrs	24hrs	48hrs
Development of UTI	2 patient	Nil	2 patient
Wound infection	1 patient	Nil	4 patient
Hospital stay days	7(6-10)	5(4-6)	7(6-10)
Vault haematoma	3 patient	1 patient	2 patient
Cuff cellulitis	2 patient	1 patient	2 patient
Vault granulation	2 patient	Nil	1 patient
Convalescence time	3-4 weeks	2-3 weeks	4-6 weeks

was AUB / DUB in 23%, POP in 20%, fibroid uterus in 19.6%, adenomyosis in 14%, adnexal mass / ovarian tumour in 9.8%, chronic PID in 7.2%, cervical dysplasia in 3.4% and endometriosis in 3.0%.

Non descent vaginal hysterectomy took the least operative time, the mean being 45 minutes followed by TAH which on an average took 1 hr 20 mins and VH 1 hr 35 min. Singh & Bansal¹² have reported an average time of 39.07 mins for VH and 45.56 min for TAH. In the present study operative time was longer, due to demonstrative and instructional method necessary for students.

Mean blood loss has been 60ml at NDVH, 150ml during VH and 250ml for TAH in the present study as compared to 35.36gm at VH and 108.5gm at TAH as reported by Singh & Bansal¹². Two patients in the VH and 6 patients among the TAH group received a blood transfusion.

No case of VH required conversion to abdominal hysterectomy. No ureteric, bladder or intestinal injury occurred in the present study. Londeen et al¹³ have reported 1.5% complications for VH, 8 to 9% complications for minimally invasive surgery and 14% complications for abdominal route. In the present study, morbidity was observed in the form of pyrexia in 2% & 3.13% and infections in 2% & 2.5% in the VH and TAH groups respectively. The Finnish⁸ study reported 2.6% & 4% complications intraoperatively, while the Saudi¹¹ study reported 9.6% & 21.6% rates of infection for VH and TAH respectively. The Nigerian report found 30.3% morbidity. Non descent vaginal hysterectomy was associated with the least morbidity.

In the present study Hospital stay has been 5 days in NDVH and 7 days in VH and TAH patients as compared to 3 days for VH and 5.2 days for the TAH patients in the Canadian⁹ study while the Singh & Bansal¹² reported 3.71 days for VH and 7.84 days for TAH patients.

Conclusion:

The route of hysterectomy for an individual patient depends on numerous factors such as child birth, POP, uterine size, associated diseases like infection and endometriosis, presence of adnexal mass / ovarian tumours, prior pelvic surgery, suspicion of malignancy, facilities and equipment available and training / skill of the surgeon. The method should be simple, easy, uncomplicated, relatively less time consuming and cost effective for removal of uterus; NDVH has been found

to be the suitable mode of surgery, meeting the above criteria.

Worldwide trends are rising towards minimally invasive approach. Natural Orifice Techniques of Surgery such as Vaginal Route remains the primary choice. It is paramount for teaching institutions to meet future clientele requirements. Benefits dictate change; for health care services lower cost. Every training programs must incorporate the NDVH surgical technique, emphasizing as well as imparting efficiently and effectively the operative procedure at all levels of medical education.

References:

1. Reich H, DeCaprio J, McGlynn E: Laproscopic Hysterectomy. *J Gynecol Surg*, 1989;5(2): 213-216.
2. Nezhat C R, Burrell M O, Nezhat F R, Benigno B B, Welander C E: Laproscopic radical hysterectomy with paraaortic and pelvic node dissection. *Am J Obstet Gynecol*, 1992;166(3):864-865.
3. Mettler L, Ibrahim M, Jonat W: One year of experience working with the aid of a robotic assistant (the voice-controlled optic holder AESOP) in Gynaecological Endoscopic surgery. *Hum Reprod*, 1998;13(10): 2748-2750.
4. Sinha R, Sundaram M, Mahajan C, Raje S, Kadam P, Rao G, Shitut P: Single-incision total laproscopic hysterectomy. *J Minim Access Surg*, 2011;7(1):78-82.
5. Richardson EH: A simplified technique for Abdominal panhysterectomy. *Surg Gynecol Obstet*, 1929;48:248-256.
6. Stark M, Gerli S, Di Renzo GC: Ten Step Vaginal Hysterectomy. In: Progress in Obstetrics & Gynaecology. Vol. 17; Eds.; John Studd, Seang Lin Tan, Frank A Chervenak. Publisher: Churchel Livingstone. 2006, pp.358-368.
7. Lundholm C, Forsgren C, Johansson A L, Cnattingius S, Altman D: Hysterectomy on benign indications in Sweden 1987-2003 : a Nationwide trend analysis. *Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand*, 2009;88(1):52-58.
8. Brummer T H, Jalkanen J, Fraser J, Heikkinen A M, Kauko M, Makinen J, Seppala T, Sjoberg J, Tomas E Harkki P: FINHYST, a prospective study of 5729 hysterectomies : complications and their risk factors. *Hum Reprod*, 2011;26(7):1741-1751.
9. Toma A, Hopman W M, Gorwill R H: Hysterectomy at a Canadian Tertiary care facility: results of a one year retrospective review. *BMC Women's Health*, 2004;4(1):10-17.
10. Abe E, Omo-Aghota L O: A decade of hysterectomy in a tertiary hospital in urban Niger-Delta region of Nigeria. *Niger J Clin Prac*, 2008;11(4):359-363.

11. Sait K , Alkhatabi M , Boker A ,Alhashemi J: Hysterectomy for benign conditions in a university hospital in Saudi Arabia. *Ann Saudi Med*, 2008; 28(4):282-286.
12. Singh A, Bansal S: Comparative study of morbidity and mortality associated with nondescent vaginal hysterectomy and abdominal hysterectomy based on ultrasonographic determination of uterine volume. *Int Surg*, 2008;93(2):88-94.
13. Landeen L B , Bell M C , Hubert H B , Bennis L Y , Knutsen-Larson S S , Seshadri-Kreaden U: Clinical and cost comparisons for hysterectomy via abdominal, standard laproscopic, vaginal and robot-assisted approaches. *SD Med*, 2011;64(6):197-199, 201 & 203.

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